

An Economic Feasibility Assessment Framework for Underutilised Crops using Support Vector Machine

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Abstract—In the advent of global challenges such as climate change and food security, the economic importance of underutilised crops as alternatives solutions to mitigate the production failure and land degradation is growing. It is however important to identify commercialization potential for these crops along with their biophysical suitability. The economic and demographic characteristics of an area that is suitable for commercial crops can also be used as a commercialisation benchmark for underutilised crops. Despite the potential of these crops, their potential to commercialisation is unknown. In this article, we developed and tested a model to predict the commercialisation potential of underutilised crops in the rural areas. The Support Vector Machine (SVM) was implemented in conjunction with a Genetic Algorithm (GA) and associated fitness functions to generate training data from models developed for major crops. We show that accurate classification results are obtainable even when the training is done with data from an approximate model and artificially generated through a Genetic algorithm which includes constraints that reflect physical conditions found in rural villages. The simulation results shows that SVM is capable of acting as a filter for the inaccuracy existed in training data which is inherently present in the approximate model thus giving good classification results.

Keywords: *Synthetic Data; Genetic Algorithm; Support Vector Machine; Economic Models; Underutilised Crops; Decision Making*

1. Introduction

Underutilised crops are generally described as species of crop which are commercially under exploited

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1 (Padulosi and Hoeschle-Zeledon 2004). Only 30 species of crops out of 100,000 species are widely
2 planted and used commercially (“The Role of Underutilised Plant Species in the 21st Century” 1999).
3 One Challenge on the way to wider adoption of these crops is the lack of research data about these
4 crops (Mabhaudhi et al. 2016; William et al. 2016). The unavailability of the data is due to the fact that
5 underutilised crops have not been widely commercialised in large scale. Therefore, the economic
6 potential of these crops in the areas that these crops can grow is difficult to ascertain. Underutilised
7 crops are important in rural areas because it can provide an extra source of income for smallholder
8 farmers.

9 Bambara groundnut is an example underutilised crop that is not successfully commercialised is
10 (*Vigna subterranea*) despite its potential as a nutritious food and tolerance to marginal conditions
11 (Alercia 2013; William et al. 2016). In Malaysia, bambara groundnut can complement tobacco as a
12 cash crop since both crops can be planted in well-drained soil with light sandy loams (“Production
13 Guideline Tobacco” 2015, “Production Guidelines for Bambara Groundnuts” 2011). In Malaysia
14 tobacco products are highly taxed (Arumugam 2017) and therefore the profit margin is eroded for
15 farmers still growing this crop.

16 To alleviate this problem, we developed an automatic classifier that is able to identify rural villages
17 that can successfully commercialise underutilised crops, based on a prediction model that does not
18 require large amount of available training data. The data for training of the prediction model is provided
19 by applying a Genetic Algorithm (GA) and associated fitness functions to synthesised data and to train
20 the Support Vector Machine. The GA generates data which emulates the properties of real data, through
21 the application of appropriate constraints relevant to conditions of local villages. The role of fitness
22 function is to represent the relationship between significant variables which affect the local rural
23 economy. In order to properly formulate this function, a literature review was performed to find the
24 significant variables and their relationship to farm income. The village that possesses characteristics
25 indicative of success in cultivating underutilised crop will then be identified by the proposed method.

1 The paper presents a framework that can be used to predict the potential of economic success in rural
 2 areas for underutilised crops based on training the support vector machine with synthesised data using
 3 a Genetic Algorithm (GA). This method along with the biophysical crop suitability assessment, can
 4 provide a range of diversification options for agricultural development in rural areas.

5 This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 denotes the literature review. Section 3 describes the
 6 methodology of the research. Section 4 addresses the experimental results and discussions. Finally,
 7 section 5 is the conclusion.

8 **2. Related studies**

9 *2.1 Artificial Data Generating Methods*

10 Insufficient data is often recognized as the main problem for poor and unreliable performance of
 11 machine learning and data mining techniques. This is due to the fact that collecting sufficiently large
 12 data could be costly and impossible in some cases (Fei Hu 2016). Studies on the impact of insufficient
 13 data with respect to training an inference engine for classification, regression and clustering have been
 14 carried out in different fields using different methods in Table 1.

15 **Table 1.**

16 Summary of related works on artificial samples generation

Related Works	Applications	Methods	Data Labelling
Niyogi, Girosi, Poggio, & Member (1998)*	Vision & Speech	Transforming and mapping of original source according to knowledge of extracted relationship.	-
Lanouette, Thibault, & Valade (1999)*	Wood pulp process modeling regression problem	Select D-Optimal Design and optimized Neural Network to handle small experimental data problem.	Theoretical model
Li & Wen (2014)*	General lack of training data regression problems	A feasibility based programming (FBP) model was built based on the data. Difference between the predicted value and the real value by FBP modelling was used as the fitness function in GA. This sample population is retained if the calculated MAPE is within acceptable ranges. These steps are repeated according to the number of virtual samples that need to be generated.	FBP model

Yanjuan Yang & Mannino (2012)*	Deception detection	Deception data was collected initially to generate more deception data. Based on the distance between the features on the data collected and the features of an ideal candidate, the deception data is perturbed within the range of threshold value and ideal value specified.	-
Wonders, Ghassemlooy, & Alamgir Hossain (2016)*	Water disaggregation multi event classification	Select maximum and minimum samples of each class from original data by adding noise to the data until the number of samples reached to the maximum selected number.	Each class is generated separately.
Jiang, Li, & Zhou (2009)*	Software reuse	Train random forest from original data, and virtual examples were added by classifying randomly generated instances, to train decision tree algorithm.	Random Forest
Barth et al. (2018)**	Agricultural Computer Vision	Generate synthetic image data of plants by rendering images using Blender software based on a plant structural model, plant instance model, texture model and scene model.	Image Rendering
Suzan & Longin (2010)*	Imbalanced data	The distance metrics known as Dynamic Time Warping and Optimal Subsequence Bijection is computed to generate synthetic data points to minority class.	Only minority class is generated
Al-bakary & Ali, (2015)*	General lack of training data classification problems.	Combining Decision Tree and Genetic Programming to generate virtual samples and labeled by Back Propagation Neural Networks (BPNN).	BPNN
Yang, Yu, Xie, & Zhang (2011)*	General lack of training data and imbalanced data classification problems	Generate synthetic data based on Gaussian distribution.	Each class is generated separately.
Li & Lin (2014)*	General lack of training data multimodality problems	Test for multimodality of the data and use k means algorithm to cluster the data. Generating virtual samples for each cluster	Each class is generated separately.
Hähnel, Hempel, & Herbst (2015)*	Evolving fuzzy classification approach	Generating virtual data from distribution function by creating values in normalized space and then translating and scaling the virtual samples in class space, which then retransform to original feature space.	Each class is generated separately.
	Wind speed data	A library to generate, maximum, minimum daily wind speed data	
Narasimhamurthy & Kuncheva (2007)*	Simulating changing environment	New data points were sampled from a distribution formed sampled from the original data.	Each class is generated separately.
Pham, Nguyen, & Nguyen (2014)***	Intrusion Detection	1. Generate nonexistent class samples from existing class samples that are out of the range of normal distribution. 2. Generate insufficient data by altering the value from existing data within minimum and maximum values of existing data.	-

Cho, Jang, & Chang (1997)*	General lack of training data in regression problems	1. Generate virtual samples by randomly pick value inside a populated hypersphere around real sample. 2. Add random Gaussian noise to real sample.	Multilayer perceptron
Enzweiler & Gavrilu (2008)*	Pedestrian image classification	Varying the shape, foreground and background of the image to produce new samples.	Each class is generated separately.
Zhan & Zhou*	General lack of training data problems	Interpolated points on several neighbour lines from the data were used as virtual samples.	-
Albuquerque, Lowe, & Magnor (2011)**	High dimensional data.	Virtual samples were randomly generated based on specification by user inputs.	Specified by users
Patki, Wedge, & Veeramachaneni (2016)*	Generative model of relational databases	The data were organized by users in such a way that relationships of multiple tables in database can be modelled into generative model. Data were synthesised by sampling from the generative model that was made up by parameters of distribution for each column and covariance matrix.	Synthesised
Enislay et al. (2012)*	Imbalanced data	Use SMOTE to generate synthetic data and Rough Set Theory to clean the synthetic data by removing data that is not belongs to lower approximation of minority class.	Only minority class is generated

1 *Partially Synthetic Data

2 **Fully Synthetic Data

3 ***Partially and fully Synthetic Data

4 Methods proposed by these researchers in Table 1 were well suited for their areas of applications,
5 where small amount of historical data is still available. In this project, there is completely no historical
6 data for the domain in question. As such, a new method for generating the relevant data was required.
7 Genetic Algorithm is frequently used to generate test data to test path coverage after software is
8 developed (Roy, Harrold, and Peck 1999; Suresh and Rath 2014; Yao and Gong 2014). Li and Wen,
9 (2014) is highlighted as the similarity between their methods and framework applied here is the
10 involvement of Genetic Algorithm to generate virtual samples to train machine learning algorithms.
11 However, the implementation is significantly different. One obvious difference is that their proposed
12 method is used for regression and our framework is on classification. In their method, small data
13 sample are required in order to use backpropagation neural network (BPNN) to build feasibility based
14 programming (FBP) model. A Megatrend Diffusion Function is used to determine the ranges of each

1 attribute. Difference between the predicted value and the real value by FBP modelling is used as the
2 fitness function in GA. Every population generated by the GA is evaluated by calculating the mean
3 absolute percentage error (MAPE). This sample population is retained if the calculated MAPE is within
4 acceptable ranges. These steps are repeated according to the number of virtual samples that needs to
5 be generated. In our framework, the GA generated synthetic data to train Support Vector Machine for
6 classification where the constraints and boundaries would be set to reflect real life situations. With the
7 constraints reflecting real life situations, the training data generated is an approximate representation
8 of the real data. Three criteria are needed to be taken into account to evaluate the methods of artificial
9 data generation. First, is the proximity of the artificially generated data as compared to the potential
10 data generated from the real situation. Second, is how feasible is the proposed method is on different
11 applications. Third, is complexity of the methods. Balancing all three criteria for a synthetic data
12 generation method is not always achievable. Data generated from the distribution function of original
13 samples (Yang et al. 2011; Niyogi et al. 1998; Hähnel, Hempel, and Herbst 2015; Narasimhamurthy
14 and Kuncheva 2007; Pham, Nguyen, and Nguyen 2014) usually fulfil the first criteria while data
15 generated by perturbation of the original data (Enzweiler and Gavrilă 2008; Zhan and Zhou, n.d.; Cho,
16 Jang, and Chang 1997) fulfil second criterion. General framework for generation of synthetic data
17 (Albuquerque, Lowe, and Magnor 2011; Patki, Wedge, and Veeramachaneni 2016; Pei and Zaïane
18 2006) have been designed to be used on different types data, fulfilling the third criterion. In this paper,
19 the GA constraints are determined by setting real life value that is found from literature ensuring that
20 the data generated is reflective of actual situation. This framework is adaptable to any applications
21 without data but where approximate models can be derived. The methodology of this framework is
22 straightforward which makes it simple to be implemented.

23 *2.2 Economic Models associated with Crops*

1 This section presents economic models of major crops such as wheat and other cereals. These models
2 mainly attempt to predict crops yield and evaluate climate change and irrigation impacts.

3 For example, a model that captures supply and demand of wheat in Pakistan was used by (ulfiqar
4 and Chishti (2010) for policy analysis. This model examined supply and demand at national level. It
5 does not take into account the village characteristics impact on wheat farming. Esteve et al. (2015) has
6 presented integration of an economic model and a hydrologic model where the outputs from one model
7 are used as inputs to the other. This framework is used to evaluate impacts of climate change on crops
8 and irrigation system. Larsson (2005) did a study on the effect of cereal aphid on crop yield through
9 crop loss model. A dynamic economic threshold was suggested through the analysis of the proposed
10 model. Crop yield prediction models were presented by Choudhury and Jones (2014) by applying the
11 models in different districts. García-vila and Fereres (2012) used AquaCrop model to evaluate crop
12 yield in response to irrigation provided to the farm. Outputs from the model were used as inputs to
13 economic optimization model to optimize irrigation system when water supply to the farm is scarce.

14 **3. Background theory**

15 *3.1 Genetic Algorithm*

16 The Genetic algorithm is an implementation based on schema theory (White 2009). Schema is the
17 number of consecutive bits in a chromosome which initially maintain its high fitness in a generation
18 and by combining these schemas the chromosome goes up the evaluation ladder. Schema Theorem is
19 expressed as:

$$E[m(H, t + 1)] \geq m(H, t) \cdot \underbrace{\frac{f(H, t)}{\bar{f}(t)}}_{\text{Selection}} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{(1 - p_m)^{O(H)}}{\text{Mutation}}}_{\text{Mutation}} \cdot \underbrace{\{1 - p_c \cdot p_a(H, t)\}}_{\text{Crossover}} \quad (1)$$

1 Where $m(H, t)$ is the number of strings matching the schema H at generation t . $f(H, t)$ is mean fitness
2 of strings matching H . $\bar{f}(t)$ is the mean fitness of the strings in the population. p_m is the probability of
3 permutation per bit. p_c is the probability of crossover. l is the number of bits in the strings and
4 $E[m(H, t + 1)]$ is expected number of strings matching the schema H at generation $t + 1$.

5 The above equation gives the expected number of schemas at the next generation. A schema has
6 length, order and fitness ratio all which are defined to a schemas number of consecutive bits. The
7 chance of the genetic operators being constructive or disruptive to a chromosome in a generation is
8 given by the above equation (White 2009; Stephens and Waelbroeck 1997). Genetic operators such as
9 crossover and mutation should manipulate these schemata towards potential solutions. The
10 specification describing this manipulation is the schema theory (White 2009; Stephens and Waelbroeck
11 1997), the longer the length of the schema, the more chances a schema being disrupted by crossover,
12 shorter schema have better chances of surviving from one generation to another. If a chromosome is
13 of length n then it contains 3^n schemata, each position can have 0, 1 or *.

14 In a study to examine mutation rate on GA, Vose (1998) found that change of value on mutation rate
15 caused great change in GA's trajectory which is not obvious to be explained by Schema Theorem. A
16 dynamical system model takes into account of both construction and destruction of schemata by
17 considering all possible ways of performing crossover and mutation. The model provided an insight
18 on the expected behaviour of generic GA that involves selection, crossover and mutation for finite
19 population. The population is expected to move quickly to a metastable state close to a fixed point and
20 stay there for some time before escaping into another metastable region depending on the fitness
21 function. This can be observed in Table 2 which shows some examples of metastable state of different
22 fitness function.

- 1 **Table 2.**
- 2 Metastable state examples

Test Function Name	Fitness Function	Generation VS Fitness Value
Ackley's Function	$f(x) = -a \exp\left(-b \sqrt{\frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d x_i^2}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d \cos(cx_i)\right) + a + \exp(1)$	
Egg Holder Function	$f(x) = -(x_2 + 47) \sin\left(\sqrt{\left x_2 + \frac{x_1}{2} + 47\right }\right) - x_1 \sin(\sqrt{ x_1 - (x_2 + 47) })$	

- 3
- 4 Metastable states are common in dynamical system where the system experiences a stable state for a
- 5 long period of time before rapid change occurs. van Nimwegen, Crutchfield, and Mitchell (1997)
- 6 introduced a mechanism that predicts the occurrence of the stable state to understand the metastability
- 7 behaviour in Genetic Algorithms. The study found that the change in metastable level of fitness (which
- 8 is known as the ‘fitness epoch’ in the paper) for a GA that includes crossover is the same as for a GA
- 9 with only mutation operator. However, at the beginning, number of initial epochs is smaller with
- 10 crossover than number of initial epochs without crossover. It is then deduced that the population will

1 not converge because crossover combines different building blocks to achieve strings with better
2 fitness. After crossover put together, the best string that can be produced in initial population, the
3 population converges to the best string. During this stage, the building blocks are mostly disrupted by
4 mutation which explains the epoch level at the same fitness level without crossover. The sudden
5 transition from metastable state to another equilibrium state after a long period of time is known as
6 punctuated equilibrium. Punctuated equilibrium describes the species evolution process where the huge
7 change caused by mutation in the genes of a few individuals that are helpful with the survival in the
8 environment, settles down to a period of little change.

9 As such we take advantage of this metastable state to automatically label our training data into two
10 classes one before the epoch and the other class after the epoch.

11 Genetic Algorithm (GA) is adaptive heuristic search algorithm with its numerical optimization
12 inspired by both natural selection and natural genetics (Coley 1999) invented by John Holland in 1975.
13 The most important element in Genetic Algorithm is the fitness function that assigns fitness value to
14 each chromosome. In our case, farm income models with economic indicators associated with crops
15 are used as fitness function for GA to generate optimal solutions. The fitness of each chromosome is
16 determined by a fitness function, and this in turn determines ability of the chromosome to reproduce
17 offspring for the next generation. After each iteration, the solutions are given a performance measure
18 derived from the fitness function and the best solution of the population will propagate to next
19 generation. This made the fitness function as the most important element in GA. The fitness of a
20 solution depicts the closeness of the solution to the optimal value.

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1 3.2 Support Vector Machine

2 Support Vector Machine (SVM) is based on Statistical Learning Theory that is grounded on
3 Structural Risk Minimization that has the best generalization capability. The concept of Structural Risk
4 Minimization finds an optimal model by striking a balance between empirical error and VC dimension.

5 Support Vector Machine is a supervised learning classifier that categorizes new data by selecting
6 the optimal hyperplane through the implementation of concept of Structural Risk Minimization. By
7 finding the optimal hyper-plane, the SVM selects a learning structure which minimizes training error
8 and generalization error at the same time. The VC dimension is related to the optimal hyper-plane by
9 the upper bound imposed on it by the margin of separation between that hyper-plane and the closest
10 data point. The structure with the smallest VC dimension corresponding to an acceptable training error
11 is chosen because the SVM picks the optimal hyper-plane. Vapnik (1998) showed that the VC
12 dimension of a separating hyperplane with a margin m is bounded as follows:

$$h \leq \min \left[\frac{R^2}{m^2}, D + 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

13 Where D is the dimensionality of input space and R is the radius of the smallest sphere around the
14 origin containing all input vectors. Hence, it is shown that minimizing VC dimension can be achieved
15 by maximizing margin from the inequality. As such, SVM still remains popular and has been applied
16 to various applications. Hyperspectral image classification (Moughal 2013), disease prediction (Galli
17 et al. 2016), and hydrometeor classification (Roberto et al. 2017) are among the successful
18 implementation of SVM.

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1 3.3 Kernel Trick

2 Many classification problems are not linearly separable in space of inputs x . In this case, applying a
3 fixed non-linear mapping of the data to a higher dimensional feature space with a suitable mapping
4 function $x \rightarrow \varphi(x)$ is needed. The nonlinear machine of SVM can be built in two steps:

- 5 1. Mapping the nonlinear input vector into high dimensional feature space.
- 6 2. Construct an optimal hyperplane of the Support Vector Machine to classify data in feature
7 space.

8 The important property of SVM is that it is represented in dual form which depends solely on the dot
9 products between testing and training points. This means that it is possible to directly compute the
10 inner product of $\langle \varphi(x_i) \cdot \varphi(x) \rangle$ in feature space as function of original input data [44]. This function
11 is known as *kernel function*.

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \langle \varphi(x_i) \cdot \varphi(x) \rangle \quad (3)$$

12 In this paper, three most common kernels which are Linear Kernel, Polynomial Kernel and Radial
13 Basis Function Kernel will be tested.

Table 3.
Kernels commonly used in SVM

Kernel	Function
Linear	$K(x, y) = x^T y$
Polynomial	$K(x, y) = (x^T y + 1)^d$
Radial Basis Function	$K(x, y) = e^{-\gamma \ x-y\ ^2}$

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1 **4. Methodology**

2 *4.1 Farm Income Models associated with Crops*

3 The approximate relationship of farm income to economic indicators for rural areas was used as the
 4 fitness function for Genetic Algorithm. This allows us to generate synthetic data when the GA
 5 attempted to optimize solution from one generation to the next generation. The relationship was found
 6 from literatures (Fujimoto 1976; Assis, Nurul Azzah, and Mohammad Amizi 2014; Hassan 2015).
 7 Details of the models are presented in Table 1.

Table 4.
 Farm income models associated with normal cash crops (Fujimoto 1976; Assis, Nurul Azzah, and Mohammad Amizi 2014; Hassan 2015)

Model	1	2	3
Equation	$\log Y = \log -0.3817 + 0.5629 \log A + 0.1849 \log B + 0.2778 \log C + 0.0239 \log D - 0.1376 \log E$	$Y = 0.049 * A + 0.546 * B - 0.253 * C + 0.206 * D + 0.034 * E - 0.038 * F - 0.012 * G + 0.066 * H + 1.141 * I - 0.442 * J + 0.492 * K$	$Y = 4.5861 * A + 3.2999 * B + 0.081 * C + 1.295 * D - 5.238 * E + 17.11 * F - 3.653 * G$
Type of Crops	Grain Crop	Fruit	General Food Crop
Area of Analysis	Kelantan, Malaysia	Sarawak, Malaysia	Sudan
Variables	Y - Gross income from rice A - Cultivated rice land value B - Total family labor inputs C - Total material inputs such as seeds, pesticide and fertilizer D - Farmer's ability index (Education, Experience, Knowledge) E - Damaged rice acreage (% to total planted acreage)	Y - Monthly income from Pineapple A - Age B - Gender C - Marital Status D - Formal Education E - Experience F - Extension (Meeting with Extension Agent) G - Distance H - Household Size I - Secondary Occupation J - Land Status K - Land Size	Y - Farm Income A - Household Age B - Household Size C - Labor D - Value of assets E - Market Distance F - Operational Area G - Weather Condition

1 As mentioned earlier, this framework is used to predict the potential of economic success for
2 underutilised crops based on a classification comparison with normal cash crops. Since variables that
3 affect commercialization of underutilised crops are approximately similar to normal cash crops
4 (Mujeyi and Chamunorwa-Mujeyi 2013). We used farm income models for normal cash crops
5 (Fujimoto 1976; Assis, Nurul Azzah, and Mohammad Amizi 2014; Hassan 2015) as fitness functions
6 for GA to generate artificial training data separately and label according to the fitness value. Among
7 farm income models, these are selected based on their village characteristics impact on farming.
8 However, these models are considered as ‘approximate models’ for underutilised crops instead of
9 normal cash crops.

10 *4.2 Synthetic Data Generation*

11 GA as a method of solving optimization problems (Santana et al. 2018; Calixto et al. 2010), has been
12 used in applications such as traffic routing (Kurniawan, Sulistiyo, and Wulandari 2015), task
13 scheduling (Omara and Arafa 2010) and recently has been widely apply in feature selection (Emsia
14 and Coskuner 2015; Behroozi-Khazaei and Maleki 2017). In this paper, GA is used as a new method
15 to generate optimal set of synthetic data on village characteristics associated with crops to train
16 machine learning model. This model is used to predict the potential of the village to commercial crops,
17 where underutilised crop is demonstrated in this paper. In our framework, using the GA to generate
18 synthetic data is more effective due to the natural way that labelling of the data can be achieved based
19 on schema theory. The proposed process to generate artificial training data is as presented in Fig.1. and
20 it is described as following:

21 1. Population initialization: Random population that follows uniform distribution is initialized.
22 Population size is set at 1000 generations. This is determined through testing with various population

1 size. Optimal combination of computation time and data size up to 51000 sets can be obtained at this
 2 number of population size.

3 2. Fitness function evaluation: Farm income models that relate crops income to village characteristics
 4 as mentioned in Section 4.1 is adapted as fitness function, $f(x)$. Fitness of each individual
 5 s_n (where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M$) in the population is evaluated. Fitness score $F(s_n)$ is generated based on
 6 the model and constraints that are defined.

7 **Fig. 1.** Genetic Algorithm Implementation

8 3. Genetic Algorithm Operators: Genetic Algorithm operators consist of three processes which are
 9 selection, crossover and mutation.

10 i. Tournament selection selects individuals randomly from the population. Individual with
 11 highest fitness value (fittest) from each round of tournament is kept. Eventually, fitness of the
 12 population is improved after each successive generation.

13 ii. Immediate crossover takes place on a pair of selected chromosomes P_1 and P_2 . Immediate
 14 crossover is governed by Ratio as following:

$$C = P_1 + \alpha \cdot Ratio \cdot (P_2 - P_1) \quad (15)$$

1 Where C is the child created through crossover and α is random number between 0 to1. The value of
2 Ratio can be scalar or vector of the length of number of variables.

3 iii. Process of mutation randomly changes a gene of chromosomes in the population to create
4 mutated child. This is to avoid current solution from falling into local maximum solution.

5 4. Termination Criteria: After each iteration of fitness values computation, the following criterion is
6 checked to decide whether the fitness value improved. If termination criteria are fulfilled, the process
7 is terminated.

$$F(s_n) - F(s_{n-1}) \leq 0.0000001 \quad (16)$$

8 5. Solutions from previous iterations: Every set of solutions from successive generation is stored. After
9 the process is terminated, these solutions are used as generated training data.

10 *4.3 Support Vector Machine Implementation*

11 In this research, Support Vector Machine was chosen because it has best generalization capability
12 compared to other classifiers as described in Section 3.2. Fig.2. shows the three phases involved in
13 implementing SVM: training, cross validation and testing. During the training phase, 80% of the data
14 generated from Genetic Algorithm for normal crops is randomly selected as training data and the rest
15 were for cross validation. Parameters of the model were tuned based on the accuracy, to find the best
16 model. The parameter used for soft margin, C was 0.5 and kernel parameter gamma, g was 0.07 for
17 RBF kernel. Real data from underutilised crops are the “unseen test cases” to predict the potential of
18 success in economic growth by planting these underutilised crops in a village.

Fig. 2. Support Vector Machines Implementation

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2 *4.4 Overall Framework Implementation*

3 The development of the proposed prediction framework can be divided into two stages as shown in
 4 Fig.3. In the first phase, farm income model with village characteristics related to crop
 5 commercialization such as population, household income, education level and so on is used as the
 6 fitness function in GA. The columns of generated data were the values of each variable and each
 7 artificial village is represented by each row of the data.

8 Real underutilised crops data collected from 30 villages in Sri Lanka is used to validate the
 9 methodology by generating artificial data using the three models presented in Table 4. This data were
 10 used in phase 3 to test the village potential to commercialise an underutilised crops, using the data that
 11 has been collected based on characteristics of these villages.

Fig. 3. Synthetic Data Generation Framework Implementation

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3 5. Results

4 In this paper, the experimental results were divided into three sections. In the first section, an equation
 5 that describes the relationship between voltage and current in circuit through experimental set up was
 6 used as fitness function to generate artificial data. Mathematical models to calculate gross national
 7 income per capita from World Bank were used as fitness function in second section. All the results
 8 were compared between Backpropagation Neural Networks (BPNN) and three commonly used kernels
 9 for SVM: Linear, Polynomial and Radial Basis Function kernel.

10 5.1 Performance Measure

11 Performance of the classifier were evaluated mainly by using two metrics which were the average
 12 accuracy and area under ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristics) Curve (AUC). Average accuracy
 13 is the average ratio between number of correct predictions and total number of data points. ROC curve
 14 plots the rate correctly classifying true positive against the rate of incorrectly classifying true negative
 15 as prediction threshold is varied. Area under the curve (AUC) were extracted from ROC curve by
 16 taking the value of area under the curve. AUC closer to 1 is denotes a classifier with near perfect
 17 accuracy and AUC = 0.5 indicates that the predictions made by the classification model is random.

1 AUC which is less than 0.5 means that the classification problem is not correctly set up. This can be
 2 fixed by reversing the predictions.

3 *5.2 Experimental Data*

4 In order to evaluate robustness of Support Vector Machine (SVM) on inaccurate models, the
 5 following experiment was set up. Ohm’s Law were used in circuit analysis to derive the relationship
 6 between voltage and current in circuit through experimental set up. Population size determines the
 7 number of chromosomes in each generation. Small population size causes GA to operate only in small
 8 search space which leads to local optimization instead of global optimization. However, large
 9 population size leads to slow computation time. In our case, population size determines the size of the
 10 artificial data to be generated. By increasing the population size, number of data points generated will
 11 be increased. Fig. 4 summarises how the increased in number of data points affects accuracy of
 12 classifier.

Condition	Model
1	$V = IR$ (17)
2	$V = \frac{IR}{a} + b - c$ (18)

Where $R = 1$

13 V is the voltage, I is current, R is resistance, a , b and c are the terms added to create the inaccuracy in
 14 this model.

15 Condition 1 is the accurate model and Condition 2 is the model added with extra terms to cause
 16 inaccuracy to the model. Genetic Algorithm is used to generate training performance for the equations
 17 to train SVM as illustrated in section above. The performance on test data is presented as Table 5 with
 18 increasing training data generated.

19 Performance plot in Fig. 4 presented how increased in number of training data generated affect
 20 classification accuracy of the classifiers. Classification performance of SVM with Linear, Polynomial

1 and RBF kernels increases as the number of training data generated artificially increases. However, it
 2 is observed that classification performance of BPNN is better when number of training data is low.

3 In order to study the performance further, slight alteration was made from previous experiment to
 4 test with completely unseen new test data. Test data were randomly generated and tested. Condition 1
 5 is where the randomly generated data were tested on classifiers that were trained with data from (17)
 6 while Condition 2 is where randomly generated test data were tested on classifiers that were trained
 7 with data from (18). The results were presented in Table 6. Condition 1 is acted as the controlled
 8 condition which represents the ideal case.

Table 5.
 Average accuracy and AUC of experimental data with population size = 20,80, 150

Condition	Population	Average Accuracy (%)			
		[AUC]			BPNN
		Linear	Polynomial	RBF	
1	20	94.41 [0.9403]	94.49 [0.9403]	92.46 [0.9403]	-
	80	94.81 [0.9573]	94.82 [0.9573]	94.09 [0.9581]	-
	150	95.80 [0.9710]	95.88 [0.9710]	96.75 [0.9886]	-
2	20	69.66 [0.9404]	73.9 [0.9507]	73.9 [0.9688]	94.32
	80	94.82 [0.9601]	79.19 [0.9846]	79.19 [0.9937]	78.14
	150	95.84 [0.9719]	82.40 [0.9946]	82.40 [0.9987]	82.40

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Fig. 4. Classification Performance of Classifiers against Population Size

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As can be observed from Table 6, SVM performs better for all the kernels as compared to BPNN.

Table 6.

Average accuracy of experimental data 2 (100 and 1000 sets)

Condition	Data	Average Accuracy (%)			
		SVM			BPNN
		Linear	Polynomial	RBF	
1	100	99	100	99	-
	1000	100.0	99.8	99.9	-
2	100	78.0	78.0	96.0	70.0
	1000	76.3	75.4	97.5	63.3

3

4

5.3 Application to World Bank Data

5

Synthetic data from World Bank was approximated to the real data. 218 sets of data were downloaded

6

for testing. The results were also compared with Monte Carlo methods and framework proposed by J.

7

Yang et al. (2011). The mathematical model to calculate Gross National Income (GNI) per capita is

8

obtained from (*"The World Bank Atlas Method - Detailed Methodology"* n.d.). Gross National Income

9

is the measure of country's income and is defined as sum of all income earned including from overseas

10

by a country. Atlas method is a conversion factor that is used to reduce volatility effect of exchange

1 rate when comparing national incomes of different countries. The following model was used as fitness
 2 function for GA to generate artificial training data as detailed in Section 4.2:

3

$$r_{t-n} = \frac{p_t}{p_{t-n}} \quad (19)$$

$$r_{t-n}^{SDR\$} = \frac{p_t^{SDR\$}}{p_{t-n}^{SDR\$}} \quad (20)$$

$$e_t^{atlas} = \frac{1}{3} \left[e_t + e_{t-1} \left(\frac{r_{t-1}}{r_{t-1}^{SDR\$}} \right) + e_{t-2} \left(\frac{r_{t-2}}{r_{t-2}^{SDR\$}} \right) \right] \quad (21)$$

$$Y_t^{atlas\$} = Y_t / e_t^{atlas} \quad (22)$$

$$Y^{per\ capita} = Y_t^{atlas\$} / N_t \quad (23)$$

4

5 Where e_t^{atlas} refers to Atlas method exchange rate, r_{t-n} is inflation rate of the country between year t
 6 and year $t - n$, p_t is GDP deflator of the country, $r_{t-n}^{SDR\$}$ is the international inflation rate between
 7 year t and year $t - n$, $p_{t-n}^{SDR\$}$ is the Special Drawing Rights deflator (details of SDR deflator is
 8 described in details in the world bank webpage with title “What is the SDR deflator?,” n.d.), e_t is
 9 average annual exchange rate for year t , $Y_t^{atlas\$}$ is the GNI in U.S. dollars after conversion from local
 10 currency and $Y^{per\ capita}$ is GNI per capita.

Table 7
 Average accuracy and AUC of World Bank data

Condition	Average Accuracy (%)			
	[AUC]			
	SVM			BPNN
	Linear	Polynomial	RBF	
1	98.30 [0.9996]	96.92 [0.9931]	98.28 [0.9936]	-
2	96.33 [0.9996]	93.12 [0.9931]	97.71 [0.9936]	97.71

11

1 Condition 1 is the cross validated results while Condition 2 is the performance of the classifier when
 2 tested with dataset downloaded from World Bank. The results show that synthetic data can be
 3 approximated by the real data and both SVM and Backpropagation Neural Network (BPNN) were able
 4 to classify correctly.

5 *5.3.1 Comparison with other method of generating data*

6 One of the common ways to generate synthetic data is through the Monte Carlo method. This is done
 7 by observing the statistic distributions of the data and generates large number of data randomly based
 8 on a given distribution (Krings 2016; Wu et al. 2016).

9 While there are many varieties of Monte Carlo method, standard process of the method involves a
 10 definition of the parameters for each feature from the original data. Based on the parameters defined,
 11 random data were generated.

12 In this section, two common methods of generating data are used to compare with the proposed
 13 methodology. The first method is data generation based Gaussian distribution. The mean μ and
 14 standard deviation σ of the data were calculated. These parameters were used to generate random
 15 synthetic data that follows Gaussian distribution. The synthetic data generated is then used as training
 16 data to train classifiers. Minimum and maximum values of each attributes were obtained from the data
 17 available for Uniform distribution data generation. Random synthetic data were generated within the
 18 range of these minimum and maximum values following uniform distribution. The results are presented
 19 as in Table 8.

20

Table 8.

Average accuracy and AUC of World Bank data (with Gaussian distribution generated data, uniform distribution generated data and method proposed by J. Yang et al. (2011))

Condition	Method	Average Accuracy (%) [AUC]			
		SVM			BPNN
		Linear	Polynomial	RBF	
1	Gaussian	88.05 [0.5031]	88.05 [0.5255]	88.06 [0.7145]	-

2	Uniform	96.1 [0.5213]	96.1 [0.5252]	96.1 [0.8925]	-
	Yang et. al	93.58 [0.9759]	89.79 [0.9564]	95.41 [0.9861]	-
	Proposed	98.30 [0.9996]	96.92 [0.9931]	98.28 [0.9936]	-
	Gaussian	36.70 [0.5031]	36.70 [0.5255]	36.70 [0.7145]	36.70
	Uniform	36.70 [0.5213]	36.70 [0.5252]	36.70 [0.8925]	36.70
	Yang et. al	92.20 [0.9759]	89.91 [0.9564]	93.58 [0.9861]	93.58
	Proposed	96.33 [0.9996]	93.12 [0.9931]	97.71 [0.9936]	97.71

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As comparison between the method proposed by J. Yang et al. (2011), two random generation methods and proposed methodology, Table 9 presents the Average Accuracy and Average AUC that was calculated by averaging the accuracy and AUC obtained across three different kernels in SVM. A performance plot of the classifiers trained by data generated from different methods are shown in Fig. 5.

Table 9.
Comparison of proposed methodology with other data generation methods

Methodology	SVM	
	Average Accuracy (%)	Average AUC
Random uniform distribution generator	36.70	0.6463
Gaussian distribution generator	36.70	0.5820
Methods proposed by Yang et al. (Yang et al. 2011)	91.90	0.9728
Proposed Method	95.72	0.9954

8
9

Fig. 5. Classification Performance of Classifiers against Different Data Generation Methods

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2

3 As observed from the Table 9 and Fig. 5, the accuracy of proposed method was greatest among all the
 4 other methods. AUC shows that the random data generator based on Gaussian distribution and Uniform
 5 distribution is almost randomly classifying the data. This is because data generated randomly were not
 6 based on relationships between the features. Hence, a random data generator based on merely data
 7 distribution function is not sufficient to reflect real data.

8

9 *5.4 Prediction on Real Underutilised Crops Data based on Farm Income Models associated with*
 10 *Crops*

11 *5.4.1 Parameter Adjustment in Genetic Algorithm*

12 As mentioned earlier, population size determines the size of the artificial data to be generated. The
 13 following section justifies the number of population sizes for the farm income models associated with
 14 cash crops in Table 4 in order to generate sufficient data without compromising computational time.

15
16
17

Table 10.

Population size vs elapsed time of Model 2

Population Size	Elapsed Time (seconds)	Dimension of Generated Data
10	0.777262	510x11
100	1.013127	5100x11
1000	3.320471	51000x11
10000	24.659098	510000x11

1
2

Fig 6. Generation versus Fitness Value Plots of Model 2 for Population Size 10 (Top Left), 100 (Top Right), 1000 (Bottom Left) and 10000 (Bottom Right)

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Table 11.

Population size vs elapsed time of Model 3

Population Size	Elapsed Time (seconds)	Dimension of Generated Data
10	0.798411	510x7
100	0.936447	5100x7
1000	2.778618	51000x7
10000	21.677956	510000x7

1

2 **Fig 7.** Generation versus Fitness Value Plots of Model 3 for Population Size 10 (Top Left), 100 (Top Right), 1000 (Bottom Left)
3 and 10000 (Bottom Right)
4

1 From the tables and plots, it can be observed that the computational time increased steeply when
2 population size increases from 1000 to 10000. Therefore, population size of 1000 needs to be used to
3 generate sufficient data, thereby making computation time reasonable.

4 **Fig 8.** Population Size vs Elapsed Time Plots for Model 2(Left) and Model 3(Right)

5
6

7 *5.4.2 Real Underutilised Crops Data*

8 A set of real data on underutilised crops from 30 villages in Sri Lanka were collected. This set of data
9 was used to validate the methodology. Among the variables of the data are family members, gender,
10 years of education, age, number of years involved in farming, land size, land ownership, distance from
11 farm to house, climate conditions and farm income.

12 Real data collected from Sri Lankan villages match most of the variables in Model 2. The income for
13 village 1 to 10 was higher than other villages in the real data set. Hence, it was expected that the SVM
14 classify first 10 villages to be potentially successful while the rest to be potentially unsuccessful. The
15 predicted labels by SVM for successful villages were indeed among the 10 villages that indicate higher
16 income. However, the SVM was not able to classify all the villages correctly due to the inaccuracy of
17 the normal crops model was used for underutilised crops.

1 The results for Model 3 are presented as the Table 12 below. Although classification accuracy shows
 2 that the model is able to correctly classify 20 out of 30 villages, however, AUC shows that the
 3 classification model is not performing better than random guessing the label. This is also further
 4 justified by observing the predicted label from SVM is biased towards class -1 where all the 30 villages
 5 were classified as potentially unsuccessful. Hence, it is deduced that Model 3 is not suitable for this
 6 set of data obtained from Sri Lanka villages as the variables involved are not providing information to
 7 train SVM. Model 1 is omitted where none of the variables match the data for Sri Lanka villages.

8 Hence, it can be concluded that SVM performs well when classifying data generated from GA
 9 through approximate models as compared to BPNN. Data generated by GA proved to emulate to the
 10 real data when both classifiers were able to classify with high accuracy.

11

Table 12.

Average accuracy and AUC of real villages data for underutilised crops (Model 2 and Model 3)

Condition	Model	Average Accuracy (%) [AUC]			
		SVM			BPNN
		Linear	Polynomial	RBF	
1	1	98.33 [0.9977]	98.32 [0.9972]	98.43 [0.9971]	-
	2	77.35 [0.4988]	77.35 [0.4988]	77.35 [0.4988]	66.67
2	1	70 [0.9977]	76.67 [0.9972]	70 [0.9971]	-
	2	66.67 [0.4988]	66.67 [0.4988]	66.67 [0.4988]	66.67

12

13 Next step was to evaluate the suitability of land and biophysical characteristics of the crop in a
 14 particular village (Sirsat et al. 2017; T A S T M Suhairi 2018). This helps in eliminating unnecessary
 15 cost and efforts to plant a new crop with the potential to successfully commercializing the crops are
 16 uncertain. Farmers will not be planting new crop unless they know that they can sell the crop
 17 considering the cost and effort that is involved in planting a new crop (Mayer 2016).

1 **6. Conclusions**

2 The main aim of this research was to prove experimentally that it is possible to train the SVM with
3 data generated from a model used as the fitness function in a genetic algorithm. In certain domains
4 "big data" is not available. We wish to extend machine learning techniques into this domain by
5 proposing a methodology with which to generate training data by running a genetic algorithm which
6 produces sets of parameters of different fitness. In our case, it is not the fittest solution which is
7 important but the set of fittest solutions which give us the opportunity to look in the real world for
8 corresponding candidates (in our case rural villages) which we propose to relevant authorities as "most
9 likely to succeed" in commercializing underutilised crops. The SVM plays the role in processing "test
10 data" obtained from real world locations and then classifying those locations as likely to succeed or
11 otherwise.

12 Genetic Algorithm was chosen as the tool to generate the artificial data because real world constraints
13 on the physical characteristics of interest to us for rural villages are easily included in the methodology.
14 It is one of the aims of this research to prove that the data generated artificially has a high probability
15 of corresponding to real villages since we include real life constraints in the algorithm and hence this
16 artificial data can then legitimately be used to train the support vector machine.

17 The results show that we have the capability of correctly identifying villages which have the potential
18 of successfully growing underutilised crops by training the SVM with artificial data generated from a
19 model which was developed for normal cash crops.

20 We intend to test using more villages as more underutilised crops are commercialised in rural areas.

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24

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6

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